

USING FESTIVALS AS PEACE-BUILDING STRATEGY IN POST-CONFLICT SITUATIONS: A FOCUS ON CATTLE RUSTLING AND FARMERS-HERDSMEN CRISES IN KATSINA STATE

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Abstract

Katsina state has had its share of violent conflicts and hostilities in recent times manifested in farmers and herdsman clashes and the brunt of cattle rustling attacks suffered by a number of communities across the state. These communities are now emerging from the crises and picking up the pieces. They are talking to one another, trying to heal the 'wounds', restore the lost love, trust and sense of mutual harmony necessary for a lasting peace. This is courtesy of Dialogue and Amnesty Committee set up by the State Government that has brokered a peace deal and now promoting dialogue among the conflicting parties in the affected communities. The committee's communication strategies include media campaign and some levels of interpersonal communication contacts, which have no doubt yielded positive results. This paper will however propose the use of cultural festivals to reinforce the interpersonal communication methods in especially promoting dialogue among the people. Cultural festivals have been rallying points and unifying forces that have held the people together since time immemorial: projecting the people's affinity and similarities, serving as platforms for physical interaction and socialisation and to certain degree bases for shared spiritual communion among the people, among others.

Keywords: *festivals; conflict; dialogue; peace building*

Introduction

Nigeria has lately been rocked by series of violent conflicts and hostilities: Boko Haram in the North-East, Niger Delta crises in the South-South, MASSOP and Biafran agitation in the South-East, tribal and communal clashes in South-West and the North-Central and the farmers-herdsmen clashes, cattle rustling and armed banditry in the North-West. The worst hit states in the North-West are Kaduna, Katsina and Zamfara. recording lost of lives and property, serious economic lost, social injury manifest in hate, disgust, suspicion and trauma. The most affected communities in Katsina State are in Sabuwa, Dandume, Fsskari, Bakori, Kankara, Batsari, Dan-Musa, Safana, and Jibia

Local Government Areas. Katsina State can be described as the luckiest of the three states to have tamed the situation and stemmed the tide of violence.. The other two states are not so lucky, the violence is still raging. In Kaduna State it has metamorphosed into mass kidnapping and broad day robbery; in Zamfara State people are still being butchered in their hundreds, women raped and abducted and entire villages being sacked. It is a gory tale and it appears there is no solution is sight! The current led APC Administration that came on board on the promise of change, particularly to restore peace and security in these affected communities and the state at large, constituted a committee for a peace settlement under the

leadership of the Secretary to the Government of the State, named Dialogue and Amnesty Committee. The 15 member Committee was inaugurated on the 13th of November 2017 by the State Governor, Alhaji Aminu Bello Masari with the mandate to meet with various gangs of cattle rustlers operating in the state with a view to identifying their grievances and advise the Government accordingly; and to consult widely with stakeholders and engage with religious and traditional leaders in order to convince the rustlers to repent and accept government amnesty (thenewsnigeria.com.ng). This Committee was able to negotiate a peace settlement that has become a ray of hope for a lasting peace in the state. In fact the year 2017 can be described as a watershed in the work of this committee. On the 15th of January 2017 the state witnessed the surrendering of hundreds of cattle rustlers with their arms. Similarly on the 10th of July the same year the state recorded the burning of hundreds of fire arms and ammunitions surrendered by the marauders at Nigerian Army 35 Battalion (Katsina Army Barracks). This corresponded with the United Nations Disarmament Day. Later on 17th of October same year more fire arms surrendered by the rustlers were burnt at Filin Polo in the city of Katsina. On the 17th of November 2017 [pmnewsnigeria.com](https://www.pmnewsnigeria.com) reported the inauguration of Local Peace Committees for the 34 local government areas across the state in order to step down the activities of the central committee., with specific mandate of maintaining peaceful and cordial relationship between herdsmen and farmers and offer useful advice on sustainable peace (<https://www.pmnewsnigeria.com>).

Lambourne (2004) however warns, “The ending of overt violence via peace agreement or military victory does not mean the achievement of peace. Rather, ending of violence or so-called post conflict situation provides new set of opportunities that can be grasped or thrown away.” It is probably heeding to this warning the Dialogue Committee has embarked upon a vigorous media campaign as a strategy of attuning the public with its activities; and some interpersonal communication efforts as part of the mechanism of engaging the affected communities and promoting dialogue among the people who were hitherto at dagger drawn. It is

therefore intended in this paper to propose the use of cultural festivals and games in order to reinforce the Committee’s interpersonal communication efforts in promoting dialogue.

Dialogue in Peace-building Process

Understanding the concepts of conflict and peace-building will enhance our understanding of dialogue in the process of peace-building.

Ramsbotham, Woodhouse and Mial (2011) in Incerti-Thery (2016: 21) defined **conflict** as pursuit of incompatible goals by different groups.” It is actually the means of attaining these differing goals (whether peaceful or forceful) that determine whether conflict becomes violent or not. Zeidi (2014) observed conflicts and differences are inevitable, but violence is not. As long as there are diverse interests and incompatible objectives, conflicts are bound to occur. If properly managed and contained, conflicts become healthy competition between parties and can promote growth and development. However, if allowed to escalate, they become violent and destructive—a social aberration to be stemmed (Maude, 2018). As Brahimi (2007:8) puts it, “Extended conflict leads to terrible human loss and physical destruction; it also leads to collapse of the systems and institutions that make a stable society function...”

The term **peace-building** emerged in the last three decades after the work of Johan Galtung, who called for the creation of peace-building framework to promote sustainable peace by addressing the “root causes” of violent conflict resolution (Ewubareh, 2014). The term was popularised by the United Nations in 1992 when it presented “An Agenda for Peace” in which it stated that one of the UN’s aims must be to: “Stand ready to assist in peace-building in its differing context: rebuilding the institutions and infrastructures of nations torn by war and strife; and buildings of the peaceful mutual benefit among nations formerly at war” (A/47/277-2411, 1992).

And since then the term has assumed different definitions and many of such definitions connote to an aftermath of civil war or post-conflict situations and therefore deeming it as a reactive measure. Jega (2018) however believes peace-building can be

proactive and can be applicable to diverse, conflict ridden or conflict prone societies, such as Nigeria, where perennial conflict even if comparatively of low intensity type, disrupts communities and undermines sustainable. It can be aimed at bringing about enduring peace or to prevent conflicts from occurring in the first place (Jega, 2018). Perhaps the definition by Adelman (2011:1) is broader and all encompassing:

The peace-building field is defined by its interdisciplinary kaleidoscope of approaches for addressing peace and conflict. From peace education to high level negotiation and mediation, from peace keeping interventions to grassroots reconciliation and trauma healing processes, peace building is at its core creative and diverse. Throughout the many stages of conflict, we look for ways to transform its violent and destructive manifestations into a more positive force of social change. In the great silence inequality of structural violence and oppression, we look for ways to elevate the voices of those who have never had a chance to speak for themselves or their communities. Among groups who have been torn apart from one another by mistrust, anger, and fear, we look for ways to bridge the deep chasms and repair wounded identities.

It is deducible from the above definition that peace-building transcends rebuilding infrastructures and institutions; it transcends provision of relief materials and rehabilitation. Peace-building is also about healing the inflicted wounds by violent conflict, repairing damaged relations, restoring the

lost trust and love and giving voice to the voiceless in order to bridge the gap of inequality. This clearly underscores the need for dialogue in the peace-building processes. As Incerti-Thery (2016) has pointed out dialogue is needed to build a state because it is what makes reconciliation between people possible. And reconciliation Faure (2006) in Boege (2006) observed is necessary for the restoration of social harmony of the community in general and of social relationships between conflict parties in particular. Re-establishing harmony implies reintegrating the deviant members and ultimately restoring good relations (Boege, 2006).

Dialogue is used in several different ways in the scholarly literature and the empirical discourse. It is often used as a synonym for more formal for a more formal negotiations between two or more parties in a conflict where the aim is to reach a negotiated agreement. It is also used commonly to refer to a more informal process ('back-channel diplomacy) of communication among opposing parties, leading up to such negotiations; and thirdly the term is used quite extensively to describe the broader peace-building processes, grassroots initiatives and bottom-up policy approaches that aim at avoiding the escalation of a conflict or crisis (Ricker, 2015). Perhaps, the definition of dialogue that fits our context is the one offered by Bryn (2016) in Incerti-Thery (2016:36) in which he defines it as "a way to relate to other people and the world at large, where one really tries not only to understand, but to understand what motivates the other person and makes them reach the understanding of the world. simultaneously you also make yourself visible and open for other to see you. In that way dialogue is a mutual process" (Incerti-Thery, 2016).

From the above definitions one can understand dialogue to be a communication process in which one tries to understand the other and why they differ in whatever respects with the purpose of creating a common ground for mutual and peaceful coexistence.

Bondevik (2016) believed for dialogue to create enhanced mutual understanding common values must be identified and used for reconciliation and peace. It is on this premise that this paper intends to discuss cultural festivals as 'bonding forces' and

attempt to explore their applicability in fostering continuous engagement among the conflicting parties in Katsina State for sustainable peace. After all dialogue is a continuous process and healing is gradual.

Cultural Festivals as Grounds for Engagement

Wiki defines festival as an event ordinarily celebrated by community and centring on some characteristic aspect of that community and its religion or culture. Festivals usually fulfil some communal purposes especially in regards to commemoration and thanksgiving. The celebration offers a sense of belonging for religious, social and geographical groups, contributing to group cohesiveness. Festivals are also very rich source of entertainment to the community (<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>). Falassi (1987) in Cudney (2006:16) defines festival as "...a periodically recurrent social occasion in which, through a multiplicity of form and a series of coordinated events, participate directly or indirectly and to various degrees all members of the whole community united by ethics, linguistic, religious, historical bonds and sharing a world view."

The Dialogue and Amnesty Committee might have met its mandates of meeting the various groups of cattle rustlers in the state; identified the grievances and might have even convinced them to repent by laying down their arms. The Committee have might equally put on hold the farmers-herdsmen in the state. The challenge obviously before the Dialogue Committee, especially the Local Peace Committees at the grassroots, is mending fences, healing wounds, repairing damaged relationships, restoring trust, etc for an enduring peace. This can only be possible through constant engagement and the most common ground for such engagement, this paper believes are the cultural festivals that are mutually shared by the Hausas and the ethnic Fulani committees across the state. This is in line with the position of Abdun Nasir (2017) that cultural festivals promote community engagement along cultural and ethno-religious lines, lessen segregation through what may be extended contact of preparation for the event. Through festivals people interact and engage intensively and establish channels of communication and relationships (Abdun Nasir, 2017).

There are many festivals mutually shared and celebrated in both the urban and rural climes in Katsina State. For exegesis of space and time this paper will only discuss Kallon-kuwa, Hawan Sallah, Maulidi and Sharo

Kalon-kuwa

Kalon-kuwa is a popular annual event celebrated in a number of communities in Katsina State to mark the end of cropping season and to celebrate bumper harvest. It is a thanksgiving celebration for a bumper harvest and a yearning for a prosperous year. Though typically a youth cultural event, Kalon-kuwa attracts people of all ages and gender. It is an avenue of 'winding out' after the hectic raining season activities. It is a big entertainment event showcasing traditional musical performances and cultural activities such as wrestling, boxing, etc. The event also provides opportunity for young men and women to choose suitors. The high point of the event is a drama staged by these young persons in which Hausa leadership positions are imitated. The characters assume the roles of the traditional Hausa leaders such as the *Sarki* (the king or emir), *Waziri* (the emir's adviser), *Alkali* (the judge), etc. they dress in traditional royal regalia and demonstrate the roles of the real traditional leaders (www.katsinastate.gov.ng)

Kalon kuwa being a big attraction and crowd puller, provides opportunity for mingling and interaction among community members and between neighbouring communities as it attracts people from far and near. Because of its cultural significance, MTN has lately ventured into its promotion across the northern part of the country as part of their corporate social responsibility and to promote their products and services. The Katsina State Government should similarly key in to support the festivals morally and financially as it does in the case of Sallah and Maulidi festivals in the state. The government should exploit the rich cultural display to promote dialogue among the people, disseminate development and peace messages especially through theatre performances whose effects are quick and instantaneous. For instance a theme for the festival can be provided annually and the celebration can revolve around key messages as captured by the theme. The Local Peace Committees, in particular, should, in collaboration

with relevant state agencies such as History and Culture Bureau become key sponsors and organisers of this event. They must however create synergy and collaboration with relevant stakeholders at the local communities levels, especially the youth groups who are usually the organisers of the events so that it does not appear like their role is being usurped. Kalon-kuwa may be an event of a typical Hausa farming community but the presence of the ethnic Fulanis is always strongly felt. In fact without the Fulanis the celebration is incomplete. The preparation and organisation of the event should therefore draw from both ethnic lines, deliberately allowing for interaction and encouraging engagement. The event can be used to arrange talks with some of the Committee members facilitating.

Sallah festivals

Sallah feasts are religious events but with strong cultural significance. They are celebrated twice annually. The first is the Eid Fitr celebration after the completion of the Ramadan Fast while the second is the Eid Adhan celebrated at the close of Hajj (Muslim Pilgrimage) activities. That is when offerings are made to Allah (SWT) symbolised by slaughtering of rams.

The highlight of these occasions are the Durbar (a procession by the Emir and his district heads and other senior councillors and traditional title holders on horseback). Durbars in Katsina Emirate according to Daily Trust are believed to have started during the reign of the first Fulani Emir, Umarun Dallaje (1807-1835). The Durbar is usually led by the Emir with the aim of expressing joy on Sallah day and to entertain people on their cultural and historical heritage. The district heads also use the occasion to pay homage to Emir and reaffirm their loyalty to the emirate. The durbar serves to unite the people, bring them closer to the authorities and give them the opportunity to listen to policy statements first hand (www.katsinaemirate.org).

In Katsina two days are set aside for the festivities: Hawan Sallah and Hawan Bariki on Sallah day and on the day after Sallah respectively. People travel long distance to have a glimpse at culture at its best. During the Hawan Sallah on the Eid day, the Emir takes off from his palace at Kofar Soro crossing the length of the old Katsina City to the Eid Praying

ground at Kofar Guga. The Emir moves in a procession of fully dressed horses in splendid colourful attire, accompanied by drummers, trumpeters, the King's Guards ('Yan kwalkwali and 'Yan sulke). This is a re-enactment of war-like situation. The procession is similar to what obtained in war settings in the past and is a way of showing the military strength of the Emirate (<https://www.dailytrust.com.ng>).

On the Hawan Bariki day the Emir takes off from his palace to Government House to felicitate with the Governor and passes on the people's messages, requests and needs to the Governor. The Governor also makes policy statements especially as regards to the people's needs and aspirations as presented by the Emir. The Emir returns home using the same route unlike Hawan Sallah where he changes route while returning to the palace (<https://www.dailytrust.com.ng>).

Hawan Sallah festivals are big opportunity for the Governor to talk to the citizens directly and the Emir to speak to his subjects. People travel long distance not just to watch the durbar but to catch a glimpse of the Emir and raise their thumbs in greeting and say, "Ranka ya dade" meaning may you live long. This underscores the high level of reverence in which the ordinary folks hold the traditional institution. Words of the 'Sarakuna' are highly regarded by the people and have far reaching influence on them. As Maude (2017) pointed out because people hold traditional institutions in high esteemed messages of serious developmental concerns from the government are usually channelled through the traditional leaders and most often disseminated to the people during the Sallah festivals. However as observed by Blench, Langtau, Hassan and Walsh (2006), the role accorded traditional rulers in conflict resolution process is entirely ad-hoc, informal and reactive. The late Emir of Katsina, His Royal Highness, Alhaji Kabir Usman used to allude to this by referring to the traditional rulers as 'Yan Kwana-kwana (fire-fighter). Meaning that the government only turns to them when there is crisis at hand. The traditional institution must therefore be central to the peace campaign. The grand occasions at state capital should be used to send messages of peace, admonishing and call for tolerance and love for one

another. The celebrations and festive mood at the community levels provide good opportunity for grassroots mobilisation. The Local Peace Committees at these levels should collaboratively with religious groups, youth associations and other relevant stakeholders organise events that will promote reconciliation and communal harmony. Such as preachings to be tailored on the imperatives of peaceful coexistence, forgiveness, brotherliness and love for one another: and cultural events such as drama and musical performances to promote the same values.

Maulidi celebrations

Maulidi is originally an event to commemorate or mark the birth of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) on the 12th Rabiul-awwal (3rd month) of the Islamic Calendar annually. The occasion in Katsina Emirate in particular used to be without much pomp and fanfare being marked by recitations of the verses of Holy Qur'an, singing of the Ishiriniya (praises of Allah and His Prophet), exchange of food and visits to friends and family, etc in all communities. In Daura Emirate however, the celebration is almost similar to Hawan Sallah in Katsina Emirate being characterised by Durbar procession, pageantry, colourful cultural displays such as musical performances, traditional games, etc.

Lately, in barely a couple of decades, the Maulidi festival has been stepped up and taken a much wider dimensioning in both content, organisation and structure. In Katsina and in most of the Muslim north and south-west of Nigeria, the festival which before now was being commemorated to celebrate the birth of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), has now been extended to celebrating the birth days of some Sufi Saints (Shehunnai) of especially the Tijjaniya Sect of the Sunni Islam.

The most notable of such birthday celebration is the Maulud of Sheikh Ibrahim Inyass, born on the 8th of November, 1900 which is equivalent to 15th of Rajab, 1320 Islamic Calendar (islamantijjaniyastructure.blogspot.com). Both the Maulud Nabiy and that of Sheikh Ibrahim Inyass are celebrated in many communities and local government headquarters in the state as prelude to the grand celebration in the state capital. The event

is similar to the Hawan Sallah festival in all the pageantry and colour, only the crowd of the Maulud is bigger and louder. The event is usually characterised by long processions of different Islamiyya and Qur'an schools, the contingents of various revered Shehunnai and their teaming followers across state. The event also showcases musical performances using modern musical instruments such as drums, guitars, pianos, etc.

The state government since the tenure of late Umaru Musa 'Yaradua as the state governor, has been supporting the Maulidi celebrations both morally and financially. It is only pertinent therefore the state government leverage on the occasions and push for the promotion of spirit of peace, love and communal harmony. Religious leaders should be tasked to preach tolerance, forgiveness and need for harmony to their followers. Celebrations at the grassroots level provide fertile ground for promoting communal harmony through interactions and constant engagement. Local Peace Committees at the local government levels should provide moral support to the organisation and preparation of such event at community levels and work directly with the relevant stakeholders.

Sharo

Sharo also known as Shadi is a traditional game associated with Fulani herdsmen who lived in Katsina and Daura areas as well as other parts of Hausaland. It takes place annually during "kaka", the harvest time at places like shargalle in Dutsi, Local Government Area, Mashi town of Mashi Local Government Area, Batsari town of Batsari Local Government Area, 'Yandaki of Katsina Local Government Area, and a host of other towns across the state (www.katsinastate.gov.ng).

The game of Sharo involves beating the upper abdomen between two individuals using long stick called "Laso". Shari teaches the young the art of combat, self-defence, endurance, fearlessness, and bravery because any wince, grimace or shiver while being beaten is a sign of weakness. It also affords young girls to choose potential husbands. The game is aimed at preserving the aged long cultural heritage and to unite the ethnic Fulani. The game is believed to have been introduced in Katsina State by

the earliest Fulbe (Fulani) who arrived between 17th and 18th Century (www.katsinastate.gov.ng).

Sharo without doubt is one of the most important cultural events of the Fulani herdsmen in Katsina State. Because of its entertaining nature, Sharo, just like Kalon kuwa, is a crowd puller. It is patronised by the young and the old; male and female; the high and the mighty and the ordinary folks of both the Hausa and the Fulbe extractions. Recognising and supporting an event like sharo by the state government, will definitely be a mark of honour and respect to the Fulani herdsmen. Such a gesture by the government will go along way in reintegrating them in to the folds of the wider society.

Conclusion

From the foregoing discussion it is obvious the bulk of the reconciliation work lies with the Local Peace Committees at the grassroots levels. The central Dialogue Committee might have succeeded in ending the conflict or at least stemming the tide of violence; but the task of fence mending, repairing damaged relationships and restoring trust among the people at the levels of the communities can best be accomplished by the Local Peace Committees who have the thorough knowledge of the stakeholders, the nuances, the climes and the terrains. This paper will therefore conclude by recommending a more devolution of power to the Local Peace Committees. They should be strengthened and empowered with the resources to successfully carry out their mandate of maintaining peaceful and cordial relationship between herdsmen and farmers.

References

AbdunNasir, M (2017) “Religious Festivals, Community Engagement and Peaceful Co-existence” in *Contending Modalities*, University of Notre Dame Keogh School of Global Affairs. Available at <http://contendingmodalities.nd.edu/field-notes/religion-festivals-and-peaceful-co-existence/>

Adelman, E (2012) “The Process of Music and Peace-building.” in Guy Burgess and Heidi Burgess (Eds) *Beyond Intractability. Conflict Information*

Consortium. University of Colorado, Boulder. Available at <http://www.beyondintractability.org/essay/music-peacebuilding>

Brahimi, L (20 07) “State Building in Crisis and Post-conflict Countries.” in *The Global Forum on Reinventing Government, Building Trust in Government*. 26-29 June 2007, Vienna, Austria. Available at <http://unpan.un.org/intradoc/group/public/documents/unpan026395pdf>

Blench, R, Langtau, S, Hassan, U and Walsh, M (2006) “The Role of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Resolution” A Field Report of a Study Conducted in the North-East Nigeria submitted to DFID.

Boege, V (2006) *Traditional Approaches to Conflict Transformation- Potentials and Limits*. Research Centre for Constructive Conflict Management. Available at <http://bergof-handbook.net>

Cudney, W (2016) “Festivilisation of Urban Spaces. Springer International Publishing, Switzerland. DOI 1007/978-31997-1_2

Ewubareh, L (2014) “Promoting Peace-building and Conflict Transformation Through Art-based Approaches: the Case of Koko and Opuama Communities in Niger Delta” Report of a Small Grant Research Project submitted to United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)/Global Environmental Facilities (GEF).

Incerti-Thery, I (2016) “Dialogue as a Tool in Peace-building: Theoretical and Empirical Perspectives,” A Masters Thesis in Peace and Conflict Transformation Submitted to Faculty of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education, Centre for Peace Studies, the Arctic University of Norway.

Islam and Tijjaniya Structure: A Brief History of Sheikh Ibrahim Niyas. Sunday 30th October 2013. Available at <http://islam-and-tijjaniyat-structure.blogspot.com/2013/10/sheikh-ibrahim-niyas-rta-html?m=1>

Jega, AM (2018) “Peace-building and Governance for Sustainable Development in Nigeria” Text of a Democracy Dy Lecture Delivered

- at International Conference Centre Abuja on May 28, 2018.
- Lanbourne, W (2004) “Post-conflict Peacebuilding: Meeting Human Needs for Justice and Reconciliation” in *Peace, Conflict and Development*. Issue 4
- Maude, AS (2017) “The Relevance of Indigenous Media for Grassroots Mobilisation for Development” a working paper submitted to Hassan Usman Katsina Journal of Arts Management of Social Sciences (HUKJAMS,) 7th Edition, Vol 2 No 3
- Ricker, P (2015) “An Introductory Chapter” in Pernille Ricker and Henrik Thune (eds) *Dialogue and Conflict Resolution: Potentials and Limits*. Burlington: Ashgate Publishing Company.
- Zaidi, SA (2014) “Promoting Dialogue for Peacebuilding Through Media and Youth Mobilisation in Pakistan” A Report of a Project Conducted Between September 2011 and December 2013 under the auspices of Search for Common Ground (SFCCG) in Collaboration with International Development Cooperation, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Denmark and Pakistan Peace Initiative (PPI).
- A/47/277-S/2411, 1992. An Agenda for Peace Preventive Diplomacy, Peace-making and Peace-keeping. A Report of the Secretary-General of the United Nations.
- <https://www.dailytrust.com.ng/news/tavel/spectacular-colours-of-hawan-sallah/154600.html>
- <https://www.pnewsnigeria.com/2017/11/06/katsina-state-govt-inaugurates-local-peace-committee/>
- <http://thenewsnigeria.com.ng/2016/11/katsina-gets-dialogue-amnesty-committee-for-cattle-rustlers/>
- <https://www.katsinastate.gov.ng/about-katsina/festivals-games/#kalankuwa>
- <https://www.katsinastate.gov.ng/about-katsina/festivals-games/#sharo>
- <http://www.katsinaemirate.org/>
- <https://en.m.wikipedia.org>